

ANALYSIS OF ASSESSMENT METHODS OF THE QUALITY OF HOUSEHOLD SERVICES

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Abstract: This article presents conclusions on the results of research conducted on the basis of methods of assessing the quality of household services.

Key words: quality of services, quality assessment methods, range of services, assessment process, accuracy, reliability, imperceptibility, quality criterion.

In the conditions of the innovative development of the economy, the process of determining and evaluating the quality of services is more complicated than the evaluation of the quality of goods, that is, valuables in material form. The absence of quantitative measurement parameters such as performance, functional description, repair cost, due to its intangible nature, in the assessment of service quality indicates that it is a more complex process.

The inseparability of the service delivery and consumption process represents the processes related to the provision of services and the actual acceptance of the results by consumers, which requires a specific methodological approach to the assessment of the quality of services. Also, the quality of services is often based on the interaction between the employee and the consumer, depending on the professional readiness of the employee, his personal characteristics and mood.

It is known that, until now, methods for evaluating the quality of household services have not been developed that are comprehensively objective. Almost all methods are based on subjective factors related to the consumer's expectations and his actual impressions, satisfaction with receiving the service. The discrepancy between the desired and actual price of the service is the consumer's assessment of its quality.

Assessment of the quality of service by its manufacturer is based on the assessment of its compliance with a number of criteria established by law or compliance with corporate standards.

Service quality management begins with planning appropriate activities. Planning the quality of services for a certain period of activity or, in general, for a certain date, means to justify the quantitative and qualitative indicators that determine their characteristics. Therefore, the planning of measures to control the quality of services and improve it should be based on reasonable forecasts of consumer needs, described in detail in accordance with their preferences and expectations for a particular household service.

After the development of plans that set goals for the volume, range and quality of services, the processes of organization, promotion, regulation and coordination are carried out, which allow:

- timely and effective implementation of planned measures to ensure the real quality of services in accordance with state, network and corporate standards;
- selection of forms of incentives for employees of household service enterprises to prevent the appearance of consumer claims;
- promptly respond to claims of services, departments and specialists regarding the quality of service provided to consumers.

A household service enterprise will be able to provide quality services if it has developed and implemented a quality management system. This system allows you to monitor the characteristics of the quality of services provided and evaluate the direct quality of customer service processes and services. For this, a certain system of indicators is used, including the number and nature of complaints about the quality of household services and claims about the violation of consumer rights during or as a result of the service. will be considered. In addition, the quality management system also provides for the existence of regulations to satisfy reasonable claims of consumers.

"I.V. Rudakova summarized the theoretical ideas about the quality management system, which includes the systematic analysis of consumer requirements, the identification of processes that help to constantly improve the quality of services provided by enterprises providing household services, and as a result, consumer satisfaction identified ways to increase the level"¹. The system of factors forming the quality of household services is presented by the author with accuracy and additions in Figure 1.

¹ Rudakova O. Yu. Methodological principles of management of services and enterprises // Problemy sovremennoy ekonomiki. 2011. No. 1.

Figure 1. Factors shaping the quality of household services

In our opinion, the characteristics related to the demands of consumer services are: waiting time and consumer service delivery, accuracy of service completion time, service completeness, level of reliability, ease of use, security, speed, courtesy, comfort, aesthetics, environment and hygiene, productivity service facilities, number of employees and duration of individual processes.

The variety of forms and directions of providing household services objectively determines the variety of methods and models of their quality assessment. Also, a significant part of the work in this field is based on the study of the conformity of the consumer's expectations with the evaluation of the characteristics of the service received in reality. Such evaluations and models are effectively used in the assessment of the quality of services whose characteristics are relatively weakly related to the material component.

The analysis of foreign economic literature showed the diversity of scientific approaches to the evaluation and management of service quality. Most of the studies are based on the evaluation of the expected results of the consumer and the actual perception of the received service, which is the evaluation of the quality of services based on certain objective characteristics. is considered correct in the absence of an option.

The GAP model, which has been successfully used in the analysis of the quality of many types of services (tourism, healthcare, consulting, etc.), has also proven itself well in the management of the quality of household services. This model was proposed by a group of American scientists (A. Parashuraman, V. A. Zaitaml, L. L. Berry). It is based on the identification and assessment of gaps (discrepancies) between expectations and perceptions during service delivery. Its importance for managing the quality of household services is to determine the causes of inconsistencies.

The SERVQUAL method was developed by A. Parashuraman, V.A. Zaytaml and L.L. Beri to evaluate the quality of services. The basis of this methodology is the quality index SQI (Service Quality Index), which is developed based on a comparison of the expected and received service quality based on a questionnaire. It includes the assessment of service quality according to twenty-two characteristics grouped according to five main criteria (Table 1): accuracy, reliability, sensitivity, reliability and empathy (empathy).

Table 1

Service quality criteria²

№	Service quality criteria	A brief description of the measure
1.	Sensibility	Perception of buildings, equipment, appearance of staff and other physical evidence of service.
2.	Reliability	Ability to deliver promised services in a timely and accurate manner.
3.	Responsiveness	Fast service and the sincere desire of the company's management and employees to help the consumer.
4.	Firm confidence	Qualification, responsibility and trust of the company's service personnel.
5.	Charity	Usability (communication with employees should be easy and pleasant), communication (the company provides information about services to consumers in a language they understand), comprehensibility (the desire to better understand and adapt to the specific needs of the client).

“Respondents are asked to fill out a three-part questionnaire. In the first part, on a five-point Likert scale, they should rate their expectations regarding the service quality criteria. In the second part of the questionnaire, consumers' perceptions of quality are similarly assessed. In the third part of the questionnaire, their opinions about the importance of the used quality criteria were recorded. If the obtained

² Developed by the author based on research.

quality factors are close to zero, then the result is considered satisfactory; their positive values indicate that the actual service quality is higher than expected”³.

The analysis of the tolerance zone is based on filling in the questionnaires described above with the third one, which determines the minimum acceptable service quality for the consumer. The tolerance zone is defined as the interval between the expected and minimum acceptable quality of service. For each quality criterion, the value of the interval is defined as the difference between the values of the corresponding estimates that are expected and acceptable.

Based on the research of L.L. Berry, A. Parasurman, V.A. Zaitmal⁴ customers were surveyed according to the five aggregated criteria recommended by them based on their evaluation of the quality of services received. The selected parameters are very general and are intended to describe the basic scheme of forming consumer expectations (Table 2). Based on a survey of experts, we have reached the results in the table below.

Table 2

Descriptions of consumer expectations⁵

Characteristics of expectations	Share in quality assessment (% of the total number of respondents)
1. Reliability: the ability to fulfill the promised set of services, the ability to rely on the company.	35
2. Immediate response: willingness to cooperate with the customer, speed of solving problems that arise.	20
3. Mutual understanding: knowledge and skills of employees aimed at establishing mutual trust and understanding with the customer.	17

³ Erokhina L.I., Skornichenko N.N. Marketing approach to the study of existing methods for assessing the quality of customer service with services // School of University Science: Development Paradigm. 2010. No. 1 (1). pp. 121-126.

⁴ Berry L., Parasurman A., Zeitaml VA. Povyshaya kachestvo obsluzhivaniya v Amerike: uroki usvoeny [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://quality.eup.ru/MATERIALY6/plusqameri.html> (Data access 10.02.2020).

⁵ Gilmanova A.R. Metody opredeleniya potrebitelskikh predpochteniy 2017. 11–14 p.; Konychev A.S., Frolova I.I. Sovershenstvovanie sistemy kommunikatsii s potrebitelyami // Innovative economy: perspective development and sovershenstvovaniya. 2016. No. 6 (16).

4. Individual approach: approaching each customer based on his personal needs.	16
5. Tangibility: the physical environment of the service process as expressed in the firm's technical equipment, personnel, and information materials.	12

Of the five criteria listed in Table 2, "Reliability" is the most important. In the conducted expert survey, the quality of the services received by specialists was ranked first, and the result of this indicator was 35% of the total number of respondents. So, reliability is the main factor of service quality in household service enterprises. If there is no trust in the business, there will be very few aspects that can attract the customer.

It can be concluded that if the enterprise constantly makes mistakes in its work, does not fulfill the promises made, the consumer will soon lose confidence in its ability to work accurately and stably. A friendly attitude and a sincere apology from the company's employees cannot change the course of affairs. Although most customers feel sympathy for a business in dire straits when they apologize, it doesn't take away the unpleasant aftertaste of disappointment. If the consumer faces a series of rejections, no matter how pleasant it is to communicate with him and how sincere the apology, he will refuse the service of the enterprise.

Consumers' quality criteria for the services of household service enterprises vary depending on their activity profile, on the one hand, they expect facts, not fantasies; not empty promises, but want to fulfill. The quality requirements of customers are reasonable and not excessive.

In household service enterprises, the current responsibility for the performance of services has a special description, and this feature makes up 20% of experts. The willingness to cooperate with the customer, the speed of solving the problems that arise, encourage more consumers to engage and try to use the company's service more.

The criterion of mutual understanding is formed on the basis of knowledge and skills of employees aimed at establishing mutual trust and understanding with the customer. According to the results of the survey, 17% of experts consider this criterion acceptable, and this feature also has a special place.

An individual approach implies an approach to each customer based on his personal needs. 20% of the survey of experts on the individual approach is correct. The individual approach has a socio-psychological description and allows each customer to implement an approach based on his individual needs.

Perceptibility is the physical (physical) environment of the service process expressed in the company's technical equipment, personnel and information materials, and according to the results of the survey, 12% of experts approved this criterion.

In conclusion, it can be said that reliability is the main factor of service quality in household service enterprises. I

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1. Berry L., Parasurman A., Zeitaml VA. Povyshaya kachestvo obsluzhivaniya v Amerike: uroki usvoeny [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://quality.eup.ru/MATERIALY6/plusqameri.html> (Data access 10.02.2020).
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